

Paper Information

Paper title	Simulating Degradation Costs in Li-ion Batteries Dispatch: Impacts on Planning and operational strategies
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Summary

Grid scale Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) have a key role for future power systems operation and stability. However, cyclic degradation, intensified by multi-service operation, remains a major challenge, directly affecting battery lifespan and profitability. This study examines BESS participation in energy markets and in automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) markets, assessing the impact of cyclic degradation costs on BESS planning and operation. The methodology involved modelling the daily dispatch of an 8.1 MW lithium-ion battery for participation in day-ahead, intraday and reserve markets, incorporating a degradation cost minimization model.

The simulations were conducted using the historical data from Iberian electricity and Portuguese ancillary services market, such as energy prices, historical reserve requirements and AGC forecasts. The results show that reserve market participation is highly profitable and can be successfully complemented with day-ahead and intraday market participation. Also, incorporating cyclic degradation cost into planning extends BESS lifespan in all cases. However, this approach is beneficial only in arbitrage scenarios, while in reserve market participation, it reduces profits.

The findings highlight the importance of balancing BESS degradation minimization with profitability, particularly in reserve market participation. Future research could apply this model to different battery technologies and real-world systems to validate the simulated results.

Keywords

aFRR, BESS arbitrage, Degradation, Li-ion, MILP

1 Introduction

The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) in power systems grew significantly with the energy transition. However, their intermittent nature affects grid stability and reliability. Traditionally, flexibility was ensured by dispatchable sources adjusting production to demand. Replacing these with non-dispatchable RES reduces operational flexibility, requiring alternative balancing solutions. Battery energy storage systems (BESS) offer a viable solution by providing multiple services to offset high investment costs (1). Among available technologies, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries stand out due to their high energy density, efficiency (90–95%), and fast response (2). High energy density enables efficient energy arbitrage, while fast response times are essential for frequency regulation through automatic reserves.

However, BESS operation leads to degradation losses, classified as calendar losses, occurring over time due to internal chemical reactions, and cyclic losses, caused by charge/discharge cycles and influenced by depth of discharge (DoD) (3). In practice, the nominal capacity decreases over the BESS lifecycle, mainly due to reduced lithium cyclability (4). BESS operation is directly linked to cyclic losses, where intensive use accelerates degradation. These losses affect capacity, lifespan, and economic viability. Mitigating them requires degradation modelling, such as optimization tools that balance profits and degradation costs to improve decision-making, extend battery life, and enhance financial returns.

This paper analyses the impact of Li-ion BESS operation under two strategies: (i) energy arbitrage in energy market and (ii) combined arbitrage with automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) services through simultaneous participation in the energy and reserve markets. The analysis integrates day-ahead planning with real-time operation, considering intraday market participation and AGC signal activation for aFRR. For all strategies, two planning cases are considered: Case A ignores cyclic degradation costs, estimating revenues without this kind of constraints, while Case B incorporates cyclic degradation costs to mitigate their impact on BESS longevity and replacement expenses. Profits are compared to assess the effect of degradation modelling on economic viability, capacity retention, and lifespan extension.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature and highlights the study's contributions. Section 3 details the methodology, including Li-ion BESS modeling, aFRR participation, and degradation cost integration. Section 4 presents the case study and results. Finally, Section 5 outlines the main conclusions.

2 Literature review and Contributions to Li-ion BESS multiservice planning, operation, and degradation modelling

Methodological differences can be observed in the models discussed in the literature that analyse BESS for arbitrage and reserve services, with or without the inclusion of cyclic degradation costs. Figure 1 summarizes the review and categorizes the main studies.

Energy arbitrage was one of the first BESS services studied, with some works incorporating degradation modeling. For instance, (5) analyzed operational strategies under dynamic pricing without considering degradation, and (6) examined arbitrage across storage technologies without accounting for it. In contrast, (7) included real-time price forecasting and degradation

modeling. However, arbitrage alone is less profitable than multiservice participation, as explored in (8–12). Both (8) and (9) combine arbitrage with reserve services, aligning with this study’s approach but without explicitly modeling degradation - (8) focuses on distribution cost reduction strategies, while (9) develops a model for European markets. Meanwhile, (10) and (11) explore arbitrage alongside other services, such as energy balancing, black start, and self-sufficiency, instead of reserves. Although less common, degradation models are also integrated into arbitrage and reserve service frameworks. For example, (12) incorporates a degradation model in its MILP framework for BESS participation in energy and reserve markets.

Figure 1 - Categorization of the reviewed literature by model typology.

Degradation modelling is classified into offline and online approaches. Offline methods assess degradation separately from optimization, as seen in (13), which applies the Rainflow Counting Algorithm (RCA) to update battery capacity and evaluate state of health (SoH) daily, and (14), which combines established models with empirical data. Online methods incorporate degradation directly into optimization constraints, such as (3,10,15), which use nonlinear programming, and (16), which approximates cyclic degradation costs within a linear framework.

The present paper study adopts a hybrid approach, combining an online linear optimization framework with cyclic degradation costs for Li-ion BESS and an offline strategy to update daily capacity loss. This method balances robustness and simplicity, meeting operator expectations.

3 Li-ion BESS modelling for Multiservice Operations

This section presents MILP-based models for Li-ion BESS planning in energy and aFRR markets, designed for easy implementation and robust performance in complex scenarios.

3.1 Energy model

The operational cost of the BESS is defined by Equation (1) which represents the difference between the energy purchase costs and sales revenues, dependent on the BESS flows set in Equation (2). $P_t^{Li,+}$ denotes the charging power, $P_t^{Li,-}$ the discharging power, $\hat{\lambda}_t^{EM}$ the day-ahead energy market price and Δt the duration of each period ($t \in T$). The objective function is subject to standard BESS optimization constraints. Charging and discharging powers are limited by the

inverter's input and output capacities, respectively, influenced by AC/DC ($\hat{\eta}^{Li,+}$) and DC/AC ($\hat{\eta}^{Li,-}$) conversion efficiencies.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} P_t^{Li} \hat{\lambda}_t^{EM} \Delta t \quad (1)$$

$$P_t^{Li} = P_t^{Li,+} - P_t^{Li,-}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2)$$

The BESS energy content E_t^{Li} is updated in Equation (3), where E_{t-1}^{Li} reflects the previous energy content, adjusted for charged and discharged energy during time period t. Equation (4) sets the maximum (\overline{E}^{Li}) and minimum (\underline{E}^{Li}) storage limits.

$$E_t^{Li} = E_{t-1}^{Li} + \left(P_t^{Li,+} \hat{\eta}^{Li,+} - \frac{P_t^{Li,-}}{\hat{\eta}^{Li,-}} \right) \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{E}^{Li} \leq E_t^{Li} \leq \overline{E}^{Li}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4)$$

3.2 Energy and reserve model

This section details the optimization of the BESS for operations under a combined energy and reserve markets framework, considering the Portuguese aFRR reserve market operation. (17). The objective function in Equation (1) is updated in Equation (5) to also consider the reserve bands.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} [P_t^{Li} \hat{\lambda}_t^{EM} + (P_t^{uw} + P_t^{dw}) \hat{\lambda}_t^{RM}] \Delta t \quad (5)$$

The sum of the upward (P_t^{uw}), and downward (P_t^{dw}) reserve bands is limited to the minimum bid (\underline{P}_t^{band}) and maximum bid (\overline{P}_t^{band}), as in Equation (6), where δ_t^{band} is the reserve activation binary variable. Upward and downward reserve bands must follow a ratio set by the Portuguese regulator (17) which ensure the TSO requirements for upwards (\widehat{UW}_t) and downwards (\widehat{DW}_t) equilibrium as in Equation (7). Equation (8) and Equation (9) update, respectively, the charge and discharge limits to reflect the reserve bands. Similarly, Equation (10) updates the maximum and minimum limits for the stored energy to consider the reserve bands.

$$\underline{P}_t^{band} * \delta_t^{band} \leq P_t^{uw} + P_t^{dw} \leq \overline{P}_t^{band} * \delta_t^{band}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{P_t^{dw}}{P_t^{uw}} = \frac{\widehat{DW}_t}{\widehat{UW}_t}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (7)$$

$$P_t^+ + P_t^{dw} - P_t^{uw} \leq \overline{P}_{AC,+} \times \delta_t^{BESS}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (8)$$

$$P_t^- + P_t^{uw} - P_t^{dw} \leq \overline{P}_{AC,-} \times \delta_t^{BESS}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (9)$$

$$\underline{E}^{Li} + P_t^{uw} \leq E_t^{Li} \leq \overline{E}^{Li} - P_t^{dw}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

To validate the feasibility of the reserve bidding, the day operation is simulated. An AGC signal is generated using P_t^{dw} and P_t^{uw} and the historic TSO activated reserve. Equation (11) updates the objective function to consider the intraday market to resolve possible infeasibilities and Equation (2) is replaced by Equation (12) to consider intraday market and AGC energy use, with P_t^{Li} set as parameter determined in the planning optimization.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} [P_t^{Li} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{EM} + P_t^{IM} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{IM} + |P_t^{IM} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{penalty}|] \Delta t \quad (11)$$

$$P_t^{Li} + P_t^{IM} + AGC_t = P_t^{Li,+} - P_t^{Li,-} \quad (12)$$

3.3 Cyclic degradation cost model

The cyclic degradation cost model from (18) was integrated into the models in Subsections 3.1 and 3.2. A penalty (λ_t^{Deg}) is added to the objective functions to account for degradation costs. In the arbitrage model, Equation (1) is replaced by Equation (13), while in the energy and reserve market model, Equation (5) is replaced by Equation (14).

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} P_t^{Li} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{EM} \cdot \Delta t + \lambda_t^{Deg} \quad (13)$$

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} P_t^{Li} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{EM} \cdot \Delta t + P_t^{band} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{RM} \cdot \Delta t + \lambda_t^{Deg} \quad (14)$$

The penalty is calculated based on the relationship between a BESS's maximum cycle life ($\overline{N^{Li Cyc}}$) and its Depth of Discharge (DoD^{Cyc}), as shown in Equation (15) and provided by manufacturers, where C^F is the number of cycles until fail. A full cycle ($w^{Cyc} = 1$) involves discharging the battery to a set limit and then recharging it to its initial level, with the DoD^{Cyc} , defined by the total discharge amount. However, in some cases, charge/discharge cycles are partial rather than complete, requiring them to be divided into half-cycles ($w^{Cyc} = 0.5$). This relationship allows estimating the cyclic degradation cost using the cost-per-cycle function in Equation (16). This cost is calculated as the ratio between the replacement cost of degraded modules at the end of the BESS's lifespan ($\hat{\lambda}^{Rep}$) and $\overline{N^{Li Cyc}}$ in Equation (15).

$$\overline{N^{Li Cyc}} = w^{Cyc} \cdot C^F (DoD^{Cyc}) \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda^{Cyc}(DoD^{Cyc}) = \frac{\hat{\lambda}^{Rep}}{w^{Cyc} \cdot C^F (DoD^{Cyc})} \quad (16)$$

λ_t^{Deg} is determined using Equation (17), which defines the cost of transitioning the battery charge from its previous state ($E_t^{Li aux}$) to its current energy content (E_t^{Li}). This cost corresponds to the difference in the cost-per-cycle function values between these two states. Inter-period analysis alone cannot determine whether the operation at the end of the simulation horizon forms a full or a half-cycle. To resolve this, each change in the energy content is considered an approximated full cycle, and a redundant counting of half-cycles is prevented using an auxiliary

variable $E_t^{Li\ aux}$. This ensures that only the discharge process is accounted for by Equation (18) maintaining that the difference between the terms in Equation (17) remains zero when the battery is either discharging or idle, and becomes positive during charging.

$$\lambda_t^{Deg} = \frac{\hat{\lambda}^{Rep}}{C^F(E_t^{Li\ aux})} - \frac{\hat{\lambda}^{Rep}}{C^F(E_t^{Li})}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (17)$$

$$E_t^{Li\ aux} = E_{t-1}^{Li} - \frac{P_t^{Li,-}}{\hat{\eta}^{Li,-}} \cdot \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (18)$$

Since the relationship in Equation (16) is nonlinear, the cost-per-cycle-function was linearized using a standard piecewise linearization method.

4 Case Study

4.1 Case Definition

A case study on the Portuguese and Spanish system evaluated the participation of a Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) BESS in the energy markets operated by OMIE, as well as in the secondary reserve (aFRR) markets – for frequency control - managed by the transmission system operator (TSO). The analysis evaluated two operational strategies: (i) arbitrage in the energy market, (ii) combined participation in energy and reserve markets. Both BESS planning and operation were simulated. Figure 2 outlines the procedure followed for each approach.

Figure 2 - Process followed for the three operational strategies in the case study.

The simulated BESS has an 8.1 MWh capacity, which meets the Portuguese TSO - REN - reserve market requirement for a minimum bid of 1 MWh. It also features a 3.2 MW power rating and an inverter with a unitary power factor. For optimal operation, the state of charge is kept between 20% and 80% of its nominal capacity. The simulation covers a one-year horizon (2023) using historical prices from the MIBEL day-ahead and intraday markets, and the secondary reserve market operated by the Portuguese TSO - REN. A 60-minute time base was used, matching the market operators' standard.

The first stage optimizes daily planning, defining the BESS's strategy for the next day in the day-ahead and secondary reserve markets. This process sets the battery's schedule for each market. Strategy (i) determines energy arbitrage scheduling, which is assumed to be followed during operation. Strategy (ii) sets the scheduling for energy arbitrage and provision of upward and downward reserve bands. These outputs are validated in an operation simulation, using an AGC signal set through Portuguese activated upwards and downwards historic data to determine the BESS operation setpoints.

In the first stage, two scenarios were considered: Case A, where planning ignores BESS degradation costs, and Case B, where these costs are included using the online approach from Subsection 3.3. The degradation cost model was set with a replacement cost of €150,000/MWh for 20% of the degraded modules, totalling €243,000. The battery's end of life criterion was defined as 3,000 equivalent cycles, a typical value for a LiFePO₄ BESS.

4.2 Results and Analysis

The results assess the different BESS strategies stated in subsection 4.1. Table 1 shows a comparison between the profits obtained and the number of equivalent cycles performed in a full year, for energy arbitrage (i) and for combined arbitrage with reserve (ii), contrasting Case A (no degradation constraints) with Case B (cyclic degradation cost minimization). In Case B, a more conservative approach reduces the number of cycles performed, directly affecting profits, as expected. Strategy (ii) shows an even more pronounced profit reduction when compared between both cases (-€91,843), suggesting that considering a cyclic degradation cost as a negative impact on the profits, regardless of the strategy. Given that the number of equivalent cycles performed is similar in both Case A and Case B, the significant reduction in profit can be attributed to the decreased reserve bands bid, as shown in the table. Due to the consideration of AGC signal activation, which imposes additional cycling on the battery, the algorithm in Case B tends to avoid the degradation cost that comes with that compliance. This results in reduced reserve offering and profit. Note that in this analysis, we assume that all reserve bids are accepted and that the probability of AGC activation is 100%. Both assumptions are unrealistic and are expected to emphasize the difference between the two cases.

Table 1. Profits from BESS market participation for strategies (i) and (ii), comparing no cyclic degradation cost minimization (Case A) vs. cyclic degradation cost minimization (Case B).

Strategy	Profit [€]			Total Reserve Band Energy Bidded [MWh]			Number of Equivalent Cycles		
	Case A	Case B	Diff	Case A	Case B	Diff	Case A	Case B	Diff
(i) Energy	163 408	158 570	-4 838	-	-	-	1 110	789	-321
(ii) Energy + Reserve	373 849	282 366	-91 483	5008	3562	-1 446	561	540	-21

To understand if replacement costs can justify on the long run the loss of profitability on the first year, Table 2 projects profits over the 3,000-cycle lifespan. This projection assumes the

same number of cycles and respective capacity loss found for the first simulated year, for the following years. The projected profit is also reduced proportionally to the reduction in capacity. For strategy (i), Case B extends battery life and increases profits by 190.26% compared to Case A. The extended lifetime (more 1.1 years when compared to Case A) allowed the strategy to reach additional operational profits. This highlights the benefits of minimizing degradation to prolong lifespan and improve long-term profitability. However, in strategy (ii), Case B reduces profits by 24.54% compared to Case A. Since under this strategy, battery request is reduced (shown by the greater number of remaining cycles when compared with strategy (i)), the impact of cyclic degradation cost modelling is less significant on the battery’s lifespan, guaranteeing almost the same operation time for both cases A and B, where the more relaxed BESS scheduling constraints in Case A led to higher profits.

Table 2. Total expected profits over its lifespan, considering the replacement cost of degraded modules for reuse.

Strategy	End of life profit [€]		Profit considering replacement costs [€]		
	Case A	Case B	Case A	Case B	Diff
(i)	434 115	591 275	174 115	331 275	+190.26%
(ii)	1 986 583	1 562 834	1 726 583	1 302 834	-24.54%

To illustrate the operation results, Figure 3 shows the state of charge (SoC) evolution and market prices on a typical day for strategy (i). In Case A, the BESS shows larger SoC swings, following price changes to maximize arbitrage. In Case B, the SoC is more stable, preserving battery capacity by disregarding less profitable cycles, mainly at the beginning of the day.

Figure 4 compares the operation of strategy (ii) in both cases, showing the planned SoC (D-1) and the corresponding reserve market bands. In Case A, the wider reserve bands provide greater flexibility for reserve activation. In Case B, no reserve is offered between hours 3 and 7. During this period, reserve prices are lower (see Figure 3), making the profit likely too low compared to the cost of a higher BESS request by the AGC. This is highlighted by the higher variability of the AGC-induced adjustment to the effective SoC (D) in Case A during that time.

Figure 3. Market prices and BESS planned SoC (D-1) evolution on March 26, 2023, for strategy (i), shown for Case A (left) and Case B (right).

Figure 4. BESS planned SoC (D-1), reserve bands, operational SoC (D), and AGC signal (constrained by reserve limits) on March 26, 2023, for strategy (ii), shown for Case A (left) and Case B (right).

5 Conclusions

This study analysed the participation of Li-ion BESS in energy and reserve markets, focusing on the impact of cyclic degradation cost modelling on the operation strategy. A MILP model incorporating degradation costs was included to assess two operational strategies: energy market arbitrage and joint participation in energy and reserve markets planning.

The results confirm that simultaneous participation in energy and reserve markets is more profitable, as noted in the literature. The integration of cyclic degradation cost modelling

reduced battery cycling, extending its lifespan - especially in the energy arbitrage strategy, where the expected lifetime increased by 16.92%. However, this constraint reduced daily profits across all market participations. In the arbitrage strategy, the longer battery lifespan offset the profit reduction, leading to a net gain of 190.26% compared to the case without degradation constraints. On the other hand, in the combined energy and reserve strategy, minimizing degradation costs reduced revenue by 24.54%. This occurs because the additional cycling degradation cost from expected AGC activation limits reserve bands offering. This issue should be more carefully addressed in the future by incorporating realistic AGC activation and bid acceptance probabilities in the optimization problem.

These findings validate the importance of considering cyclic degradation in BESS operation planning, particularly for energy arbitrage strategies, prone to higher BESS cycling. However, for reserve market participation, applying operational constraints to reduce degradation may compromise economic viability.

For practical applications, BESS operation strategies can be improved by refining piecewise linearization with more segments while maintaining computational efficiency. Extending the model to longer time horizons or markets with different time bases could also provide further insights.

Future research can apply this model to other BESS types, such as flow batteries or even hybrid systems, which have different degradation characteristics and efficiencies. These technologies could address some limitations of Li-ion batteries, such as cyclic degradation, and provide alternative energy storage solutions. Finally, testing the model in real BESS systems would help validate the results and improve operational strategies to increase profitability and extend battery life.

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Bibliography

1. Günter N, Marinopoulos A. Energy storage for grid services and applications : Classification , market review , metrics , and methodology for evaluation of deployment cases. *Journal of Energy*. 2016;8:226–34.
2. Khan SA, Hussain I, Thakur AK, Yu S, Lau KT, He S, et al. Advancements in battery thermal management system for fast charging/discharging applications. *Energy Storage Mater*. 2024 Feb;65:103144.

3. Loew S, Anand A, Szabo A. Economic model predictive control of Li-ion battery cyclic aging via online rainflow-analysis. *Energy Storage*. 2021 Jun 17;3(3).
4. Keil P, Schuster SF, Wilhelm J, Travi J, Hauser A, Karl RC, et al. Calendar Aging of Lithium-Ion Batteries. *J Electrochem Soc*. 2016 Jul 6;163(9):A1872–80.
5. Telaretti E, Ippolito M, Dusonchet L. A Simple Operating Strategy of Small-Scale Battery Energy Storages for Energy Arbitrage under Dynamic Pricing Tariffs. *Energies (Basel)*. 2015 Dec 25;9(1):12.
6. Pelzer D, Ciechanowicz D, Knoll A. Energy arbitrage through smart scheduling of battery energy storage considering battery degradation and electricity price forecasts. In: 2016 IEEE Innovative Smart Grid Technologies - Asia (ISGT-Asia). IEEE; 2016. p. 472–7.
7. Zhang X, Qin C (Chris), Loth E, Xu Y, Zhou X, Chen H. Arbitrage analysis for different energy storage technologies and strategies. *Energy Reports*. 2021 Nov;7:8198–206.
8. Agrela JC, Rezende I, Soares T. Analysis of battery energy storage systems participation in multi-services electricity markets. In: 2022 18th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM). IEEE; 2022. p. 1–6.
9. Pandžić K, Pavić I, Andročec I, Pandžić H. Optimal Battery Storage Participation in European Energy and Reserves Markets. *Energies (Basel)*. 2020 Dec 15;13(24):6629.
10. Singh A, Pareek P, Sampath LPMI, Goel L, Gooi HB, Nguyen HD. A Stress-Cognizant Optimal Battery Dispatch Framework for Multimarket Participation. *IEEE Trans Industr Inform*. 2024 May;20(5):7259–68.
11. Hashmi MU, Pereira L, Busic A. Energy storage in Madeira, Portugal: co-optimizing for arbitrage, self-sufficiency, peak shaving and energy backup. In: 2019 IEEE Milan PowerTech. IEEE; 2019. p. 1–6.
12. Mirzaei Alavijeh N, Khezri R, Mazidi M, Steen D, Le AT. Profit benchmarking and degradation analysis for revenue stacking of batteries in Sweden's day-ahead electricity and frequency containment reserve markets. *Appl Energy*. 2025 Mar;381:125151.
13. Fioriti D, Scarpelli C, Pellegrino L, Lutzemberger G, Micolano E, Salamone S. Battery lifetime of electric vehicles by novel rainflow-counting algorithm with temperature and C-rate dynamics: Effects of fast charging, user habits, vehicle-to-grid and climate zones. *J Energy Storage*. 2023 Mar;59:106458.
14. Xu B, Oudalov A, Ulbig A, Andersson G, Kirschen DS. Modeling of Lithium-Ion Battery Degradation for Cell Life Assessment. *IEEE Trans Smart Grid*. 2018 Mar;9(2):1131–40.
15. Bai Y, Wang J, He W. Energy arbitrage optimization of lithium-ion battery considering short-term revenue and long-term battery life loss. *Energy Reports*. 2022 Dec;8:364–71.
16. Lee JO, Kim YS. Novel battery degradation cost formulation for optimal scheduling of battery energy storage systems. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*. 2022 May;137:107795.

17. Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços Energéticos. Manual de Procedimentos da Gestão Global do Sistema. Diário da República, 2a Série, 247 Portugal; Nov 26, 2023.
18. Lee JO, Kim YS. Novel battery degradation cost formulation for optimal scheduling of battery energy storage systems. International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems. 2022 May;137:107795.